

Discourse, Communication and Society Language Analyser

MANUAL AND SOFTWARE - <https://dicos-la.com/>

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DiCoS-LA (Discourse, Communication and Society Language Analyser) is a web-based tool designed for the processing and analysis of written texts, with a particular focus on managing and exploring linguistic corpora. The platform targets both researchers and the general public, offering an intuitive interface that supports text exploration, filtering, and detailed analysis.

The tool allows users to work with corpora hosted on the platform as well as with temporary texts uploaded for analysis. The central philosophy behind DiCoS-LA is to provide a fast and streamlined user experience, ensuring that both current and future functionalities integrate seamlessly without compromising system performance.

Originally conceived as a support tool for the linguistic research team 'Discourse, Communication and Society' (DiCoS) at the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC), DiCoS-LA has evolved into a more versatile application, now catering to a wider audience interested in textual analysis. Still, it is still in beta version awaiting for funding to improve certain features.

At present, the application supports the analysis of both user-uploaded texts and documents stored within server-hosted corpora. It also features an advanced filtering system that facilitates the extraction of texts and relevant information for subsequent analysis. For linguistic tasks, DiCoS-LA offers a **KWIC (Keywords in Context)** panel, which enables users to examine the surrounding context of words, phrases, full sentences, and even punctuation marks. In addition, the platform includes a reading panel for in-depth text navigation and another dedicated to a variety of linguistic analyses.

Technical Details. Technologies Used

Programming Language: Python

Python was chosen as the primary language for backend development due to its simplicity and power. Its extensive set of libraries and frameworks makes it ideal for data processing, implementing linguistic algorithms, and integrating various components of the application.

Framework: Django

Django was selected to build the web application. It simplifies backend management and provides a scalable structure. Its “batteries included” philosophy allowed the team to reduce development time by offering built-in tools for database handling, user authentication, and view management.

Database: SQLite

SQLite was selected to store user data and other relevant application information. Its simplicity and easy configuration make it ideal for the initial stages of development and deployment. Moreover, SQLite stores all data in a single file, which simplifies management and reduces maintenance complexity.

Frontend: HTML, CSS, and JavaScript

The DiCoS-LA user interface was developed using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript to ensure a clear and effective user experience. HTML and CSS provide structure and design, while JavaScript enables interactive elements that enhance usability. The interface follows a minimalist design that prioritizes functionality without compromising clarity.

JavaScript Libraries and Frameworks: React

React was implemented to provide greater dynamism and responsiveness in the user interface. It facilitates the creation of reusable components, contributing to a smooth and responsive user experience by reducing load times and enhancing interaction with the analysis panels.

Search Engine: ElasticSearch

ElasticSearch was integrated to optimize filtering and information retrieval within the corpora. This powerful tool allows for fast and complex searches, even across large volumes of text—an essential feature for advanced textual analysis in DiCoS-LA.

Linguistic Processing: NLTK

The NLTK library was used for linguistic processing. It offers essential tools for text analysis, including tokenization, parsing, and other key functions necessary for working with corpora.

Containers: Docker

Docker was employed to facilitate deployment and scalability. It allows the various components of DiCoS-LA to be managed and deployed consistently, minimizing configuration issues and enabling a smoother transition between development, testing, and production environments.

Web Server: Apache HTTP Server

Apache HTTP Server was selected to handle user requests and serve static content. Its flexibility, thanks to a wide range of modules, makes it highly customizable and adaptable to project needs. It's a robust and widely used option, ensuring reliable performance and efficient management of concurrent connections.

Version Control: Git

Git was the version control system used to manage the source code. It enabled efficient collaboration among team members and provided detailed tracking of changes throughout the development process.

Development Environment: Visual Studio Code

Visual Studio Code was the main development environment due to its flexibility, extensibility, and ease of use. Its wide array of extensions helped integrate the technologies used and boosted productivity during the project's development.

System Architecture

Simple Explanation

DiCoS-LA is a web tool designed for processing and analysing texts. It follows a client-server architecture where the frontend (built with HTML, CSS, and JavaScript) interacts with a backend developed in Django. Users can upload texts or work with corpora stored on the server. User data is stored in an SQLite database, while corpora are indexed with Elasticsearch to allow for complex queries. Apache HTTP Server manages incoming requests and serves content. Linguistic analysis is performed using the NLTK library, which enables in-depth text exploration and the generation of meaningful results for interpretation.

Extended Explanation

Frontend

The frontend is the part of DiCoS-LA that users interact with directly. It was developed using HTML, CSS, and JavaScript, with React integrated to offer a dynamic and responsive experience. HTML and CSS ensure that the layout and design are clean and accessible, while JavaScript and React enable interactive elements and reusable components that enhance navigation and interactivity. The interface includes panels for data visualisation, file uploads, and advanced filtering tools—each designed to streamline and enhance the textual analysis workflow.

Backend

The backend of DiCoS-LA was developed in Python using the Django framework. It handles the core logic of the application, manages user authentication, processes incoming requests, and coordinates the various features offered. When a user performs an action via the interface, the backend processes the request, applies the relevant business rules, and—if needed—queries the database or search engine. Django makes it easy to implement complex logic, manage HTTP requests, and integrate with other components, ensuring the system remains robust and scalable.

Database

DiCoS-LA uses SQLite for data storage. This lightweight database stores user-related information—such as credentials and preferences—as well as other data relevant to the application. SQLite is ideal for initial development stages because it requires no complex server configuration, making data handling both simple and efficient.

Search Engine

The system incorporates Elasticsearch as its search engine to support fast and efficient querying across large volumes of text. Elasticsearch indexes the corpora in a way that enables complex, high-speed searches. This functionality is essential for the type of advanced textual analysis

DiCoS-LA provides, delivering immediate and accurate results for searches involving words, phrases, or specific patterns. Its optimization for handling large-scale text data makes it a perfect solution for corpus-based linguistic research.

Web Server

DiCoS-LA relies on Apache HTTP Server to manage web requests. Apache receives and processes user HTTP requests, serves static content like HTML, CSS, and JavaScript files, and forwards dynamic requests to the Django backend. Known for its flexibility and configurability, Apache is well suited to the project's needs and ensures reliable performance even under variable server loads. It plays a key role in keeping the application accessible and stable.

Main Components

User Interface

The DiCoS-LA user interface begins with a main menu and a navigation bar. This bar allows users to access different sections, log in, view the application logo, and use action buttons based on their permission level. Authorized users can upload temporary data or access the corpus. For users with corpus access, the interface includes an advanced search window offering several options for corpus exploration.

The **KWIC panel (Keywords in Context)** includes sections for text selection, a context table, and a control panel with all necessary options for searching within uploaded or stored texts. There is also a **full-text view** for comfortable reading of entire texts, and an **analytics tab** that presents additional analyses, such as collocation analysis, complete with dedicated tables and visual components.

Backend / Server

The backend, built in Django, manages user authentication, text processing, and corpus operations. During login, users provide a username and password, which are checked against the database. If valid, access is granted; otherwise, users are informed whether the username does not exist or the password is incorrect. Password recovery is also supported via a code sent to the email provided at registration.

During user registration, a username, password (with confirmation), and valid email are required. Only if all criteria are met is the account created. For text processing and corpus handling, when a user initiates a search, the system extracts relevant data based on specified parameters and sends a **query** to Elasticsearch. The resulting data can be further processed, often involving **tokenization** and analysis via the **NLTK** library.

Storage

Documents are stored in indexed formats, each with fields such as title, author name, publication date, and genre, which are used to support future searches. Elasticsearch indexes these documents to enable fast and efficient retrieval. User data, on the other hand, is managed through SQLite. This includes encrypted usernames and passwords, user roles (defaulting to basic), and potentially expandable data such as search history or favourites. SQLite's simplicity makes it well-suited to applications that don't require large-scale database infrastructure.

Analysis Engine

The DiCoS-LA analysis engine runs on **NLTK**, a powerful Python library for linguistic processing. During a search, NLTK handles tokenization—that is, splitting texts into words or phrases for analysis. It also detects specific patterns such as keywords, collocations, and other linguistic features that users can explore in the **analytics** section. These capabilities help users better understand content and identify linguistic patterns across corpora.

Component Interaction

All components in the DiCoS-LA system communicate in a coordinated way. When a user interacts with the interface, a request is sent to the backend, which processes it and applies the appropriate logic. If the request involves searching the corpus, the backend generates a query and sends it to ElasticSearch, which retrieves the matching data. These results are then processed and returned to the frontend, where they are displayed via context panels, data tables, or full-text visualizations. The SQLite database is also accessed during this process to manage user credentials and preferences, ensuring a personalised experience.

Application Features

'Home' Tab

Figure 1: Main 'Home' Tab

Following the top-to-bottom layout of the interface, the first element is the **navigation bar**. This bar updates dynamically as new features are implemented. On the far left, the application name is always visible. As users access different sections, new tabs are added progressively toward the right. On the far right, you'll find the **Options**, **Log In**, and **Sign Up** buttons. The **Options** button offers basic controls for the application, while the other two manage user access, allowing users to create an account or log into the system.

This interface corresponds to the **beta version** of the application, which already includes the essential features needed by the development team. However, ongoing improvements will be incorporated progressively as the project evolves through usage and feedback.

At the center of the screen is the **DiCoS-LA logo**, which features the acronym of the research group alongside the reference to *Language Analyser*, the application's main purpose (though, as explained later, it offers additional capabilities). The logo's color scheme—**blue and orange on a**

white background—represents the University of Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC). Just below the logo, the full wording of the acronym is displayed.

Beneath the logo, a set of **action buttons** allows users to perform key operations in the application:

- **Add:** Lets users input a text directly or add it via a link.
- **Corpus:** Provides access to browse files in the corpus.
- **Open:** Opens documents from the local device and loads them temporarily into the session.
- **Upload:** Uploads files to the corpus or allows users to create a new one.

Note that the **Upload** function is only available to users with **editor or administrator privileges**, a detail further explained in later sections.

Colour Scheme

The default colour theme is **white**, with **blue** used to highlight important elements (e.g., buttons and tables) and **orange** applied to more specific or distinctive functions. Orange is also used occasionally to denote contrasting actions—for instance, blue to proceed and orange to go back. In **dark mode**, colours are adapted to darker tones to reduce visual fatigue, while maintaining the same chromatic logic.

Options Buttons

Add Text – *Button: Add, see Figure 2.*

This button allows users to temporarily add plain text to the session. If the text contains the necessary attributes in the specified format—**[key:value]**—those attributes are extracted and used to fill the document’s metadata. If not, the system will automatically retrieve key information (title, short title, and content) directly from the plain text.

Figure 2: 'Add Text' Pop-up Window

As shown in **Figure 2**, the **'Scrape URLs'** button is highlighted in orange—an intentional design choice that reflects its distinct functionality. Unlike the standard actions of **'Accept'** (blue) or **'Cancel'** (grey), this button triggers a different way of adding text—via URLs. The use of orange here visually signals that this option diverges from the typical workflow.

When clicked, this button opens a new window, shown in **Figure 3**, which allows users to add texts by extracting the main content from the web pages associated with the entered URLs.

Figure 3: 'Scrape URLs' Pop-up Window

Select Corpus – Button: Corpus.

This button allows users to choose one of the available corpora and work with the documents it contains. Once a corpus is selected, clicking the **Accept** button (as shown in **Figure 4**) will take the user to the **Search** window. This window can only be accessed through the **Corpus** button and is used to search for specific files within the selected corpus.

Figure 4: 'Corpus' Pop-up Window (1)

Open Files – Button: Open

This option allows users to upload files directly from their computer. Similar to the **Add Text** function, it extracts plain text from the uploaded file. If the first line contains attributes, the system uses them; otherwise, it derives the necessary information from the content itself to populate the fields required for the application to function properly.

These documents are added **temporarily**, meaning they will be removed from the session once the user logs out or returns to the Home tab and selects different files or explores the corpus.

As shown in **Figure 5**, in addition to the **Cancel** button, there are two further options that allow users to open **two different types of text files**. The first is for standard plain text with no special formatting beyond the optional attributes that the system may detect. The second option is for **texts that have been normalised using VARD 2**. These files require special processing to clean the text and also allow the system to apply **tags to normalised words**, showing both the updated form and the original variant

Figure 5: 'Open' Pop-up Window

Upload Files – Button: Upload

This button allows users to add files to an existing corpus or to create new corpora by uploading files tagged as belonging to them. This option is only available to users with **elevated permissions**, as it involves direct interaction with the application's database by adding or modifying corpus files.

It is important to note that users with these permissions may **add or update files**, but they **cannot delete** files or entire corpora. The ability to delete files or corpora is **restricted to administrator-level users only**.

Figure 6: 'Upload' Pop-up Window

Automatic Upload functions similarly to the **Open** button, allowing files to be processed as long as they contain the minimum required attributes to be added to a corpus—specifically: **corpus name, title, author, and content**. The user is notified about which files were successfully added and which were not.

If the user clicks **Hand Upload**, a form opens to manually input the document's metadata field by field (see **Figure 7**). In this form, mandatory fields are marked with an asterisk (*). If any of these fields are missing or invalid, the file cannot be uploaded to the corpus.

Figure 7: Upload Form

Search Tab

The **Search** tab serves as the application's main search engine. It allows users to **filter documents** based on desired values for each available attribute, as illustrated in **Figure 8**. This feature represents one of the core components of the application and includes a **custom-built search method** that leverages Elasticsearch.

The aim is to provide the research team and corpus-authorized users with a powerful, efficient tool for locating and filtering documents—while also ensuring fast loading and seamless integration into the application workflow.

The screenshot shows the 'Search Menu' interface. It has a blue header with 'DiCoS-LA', 'Home', and 'Search' links. Below the header is a 'Search Menu' section with a grid of filter categories: Title, Author, Sex, Year, Century, Genre, Place of Publication, Publishing House, Topic, Variants, Transcriber, and Tags. Each category contains a list of items with checkboxes. The 'Tags' category is highlighted in orange and contains one item, 'Tag de prueba'. Below the filters is a 'Content:' field for entering search terms, and an 'Advanced search parameters:' field with an example: '@author:shakespeare year:1590 | 1611'. A 'Search' button is located at the bottom left of the search area.

Figure 8: 'Search Menu' Tab

This tab can only be accessed when working with files from **corpora already uploaded to the platform**, as all other methods operate using files stored **temporarily** in the user's session or in the browser itself.

In the image, we can see several **checkboxes** corresponding to the indexed attributes of the documents. Users can select one, multiple, or none of the options for each checkbox. This allows for a **more refined and detailed search**. If no option is selected and no text is entered in the text fields described below, **all documents** from the selected corpus will be retrieved.

In this case, the color **orange** is used to highlight the **tags checkbox**, as its function is different from the others. Texts added to the corpus may include **tags**, which follow the format: [% tag title %] text associated with the tag [% endtag %].

When a tag is selected, the system will:

1. Extract documents containing that tag and matching any other selected attributes.
2. Display and work only with the **tagged segment of the text** rather than the entire document.

In addition to these options, there are **two more filters**:

- **Content:** Allows users to search for specific phrases or expressions within the text.
- **Advanced Search Parameters:** An advanced query field that supports filtering using a simple syntax.

The syntax allows filtering by any of the fields listed in the checkboxes above:

- @ specifies the field to be searched, followed by a colon :
- [] denotes a **range**, with values separated by commas ,
- | acts as a logical **OR**
- , (outside brackets) lists **multiple values**
- ! represents **NOR**, excluding the value that follows

An example of this syntax is shown in **Figure 9**:

Figure 9: Example of Search Parameters

KWIC Panel Tab

This tab includes a **custom-built system** designed specifically for **contextual search**. It allows users to:

- Select files from those retrieved through the previous **Search** tab,
- Or from documents added via **Add** or **Open**,
- Read document content,
- Search and filter textual contexts,
- And display the results in a **context table**.

All these features are shown in **Figure 10**

The KWIC Panel Tab interface includes a navigation bar at the top with 'DICO-S-LA', 'Home', 'Search', 'KWIC', 'Full text', and 'Analytics'. The main panel is titled 'KWIC Panel' and contains a 'Documents' list on the left, a 'Document' preview window, a table of document statistics, and a 'Parameters' section for search refinement.

#	Title	Word Count	Vocab Density	Words/Sentence
1	The New Family Receipt-Book, containing seven hundred truly valuable receipts in various branches of domestic economy	20414	0.15	21.09
2	The family friend, a young woman's companion; or, housekeeper's instructor: containing a very complete collection of original and approved receipts in every branch of cookery, confectionary, &c.; &c	31087	0.11	34.58
3	The modern cookery: written upon the most approved and economical principles, and in which every receipt has stood the test of experience	19783	0.12	32.86
4	The Virginia House-Wife. Method is the soul of management	25057	0.12	34.37
5	The cook's complete guide, on the principles of frugality, comfort, and elegance: including the art of carving and the most approved method of setting-out a table, explained by numerous copper-plate engravings: instructions for preserving health and attaining old age: with directions for breeding and fattening all sorts of poultry and for	6720	0.31	21.82

Figure 10: KWIC Panel Tab

Below is a breakdown of the different sections within this complex panel. While it may seem elaborate, it has been intentionally designed with **simplicity and ease of use** in mind. That said, there is quite a bit of functionality to understand.

As shown in **Figure 11**, this first element is a **checkbox list** containing the titles of documents retrieved via **Search** or temporarily uploaded through the application. Users can select the specific texts they wish to include in their contextual searches.

This feature has several potential uses. For instance, users may first run a broader search and then **selectively narrow down** the set of documents for context-based queries. This avoids the need to start a new search from scratch and saves considerable time and effort—reducing the task to just a few clicks.

All other components of the KWIC panel will update dynamically based on the selections made in this section.

The 'Documents' section shows a list of document titles with checkboxes. The first three items are checked: 'The New Family Receipt-Book...', 'The family friend, a young woman's companion...', and 'The modern cookery...'. The 'Done' button is highlighted in blue.

Figure 11: Documents Checkbox

In the next figure, we see a **table** that allows users to **navigate through each of the selected texts**. To optimise resource usage and processing time, documents are displayed **one at a time** in the **content table** (see **Figure 13**).

The content shown in this table can also be changed by clicking on any **row** in the **context table**, which will redirect the user to the corresponding context.

Additionally, key information about each document is displayed, including:

- **Word count**
- **Lexical density**
- **Average words per sentence**

#	Title	Word Count	Vocab Density	Words/Sentence
1	The New Family Receipt-Book, containing seven hundred truly valuable receipts in various branches of domestic economy	20414	0.15	21.09
2	The family friend, a young woman's companion; or, housekeeper's instructor: containing a very complete collection of original and approved receipts in every branch of cookery, confectionary, &c.; &c	31087	0.11	34.58
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Figure 12: Content Selection

In the **content table** (Figure 13), users not only see each of the selected texts—once they've been chosen or once a specific context has been accessed—but also the **highlighted word, phrase, or expression** whose context is being analysed.

By default, the word **"put"** appears, as it is the most frequently occurring term in the corpus used for this example. Special care has been taken to **optimise processing and loading times**. When a document is loaded, the entire text is **tokenised**, which enables the system to:

- Identify the most frequent words,
- Determine the type of each word in the document content,
- And eliminate redundant processing during searches.

Although this may slightly increase the time it takes to upload files to the corpus or to load them temporarily, it significantly enhances the **speed and smoothness** of the user experience when analysing content.

cloves, mace, nutmeg, pepper and pimento; **put** it in a small stew-pot with very strong beef gravy, with port and equal quantity of madeira or sherry. It must be covered—stew till tender, then take out the lamprey and keep hot, while you boil up the liquor with two or three anchovies chopped and some flour and butter, strain the gravy through a sieve, and add lemon juice and some made mustard. Serve with sippets of bread and horse radish. Eels, seals, and carp, done the same way, are excellent. When there is spawn, it must be fried and **put** round. Note. Cyder instead of white wine will do in common. Eel Pye. Cut the eels in lengths of two or three inches, season with pepper and salt, and place in the dish, with some bits of butter and a little water—and cover it with paste. Spitchcock Eels. Take a large one, leave the skin on, cut it in pieces of four inches long, open it on the belly side and clean it nicely—wipe it dry, and then wet it with a beaten egg, and strew it over on both sides with chopped parsley, pepper, salt, a very little sage and a bit of mace pounded fine and mixed with tire seasoning. Rub the gridiron with a bit of suet, and broil the fish of a fine colour. Serve with anchovy and butter for sauce. Fried Eels. If small, they should be curled round and fried, being first dipped in egg and crumbs o bread. Boiled Eels. The small ones are preferable, do them in a small quantity of water, with a good deal of parsley, which should be served up with them and me liquor. Serve chopped parsley and butter for sauce. Eel Broth. Very nourishing for the sick. As above; but to be stewed two hours, and an onion; and pepper-corns added—salt to taste. Collared Eel. Bone a large eel, but don ' t skin it, mix pepper, salt, mace, pimento, and a clove or two, in the finest powder, and rub over the whole inside, roll it tight, and bind it with a coarse tape. Boil in salt and water till enough, then add vinegar, and when cold, keep the collar in pickle. Serve it whole or in slices, garnished with parsley. Chopped sage, parsley, and a little thyme, knotted marjoram, and savory, mixed with the spices, greatly improve the taste. Perch and Tench. **Put** them in cold water, boil them carefully, and serve with melted butter and soy. Mackerel. Boiled, and served with butter and fennel. Broiled, being split and sprinkled with herbs, pepper and salt—or stuffed with the same, crumb

Figure 13: Content Area

The system automatically **scrolls** to the **highlighted word** in the document, although users can always **manually scroll** to any other part of the text. Word types are displayed via **tooltip** when hovering over them with the mouse, using a **colour-coded guide**:

- **Red:** nouns
- **Orange:** verbs
- **Yellow:** adjectives
- **Light green:** adverbs
- **Dark green:** modals
- **Blue:** pronouns
- **Purple:** determiners
- **Violet:** conjunctions

Words that do not fall into these categories are left uncoloured but are marked with the **"Other"** label as their POS tag.

As previously noted, the **context table (Figure 14)** displays all identified contexts. Clicking on any of these rows directs the user to the corresponding location within the full text. The **amount of text shown** on either side of the searched word or phrase ranges from **5 to 50 words**. On the left, the **short title** of the source document is also displayed.

Document	Left	Context	Right
The New Family Receipt-Book	mace, nutmeg, pepper and pimento;	put	it in a small stew-pot with
The New Family Receipt-Book	it must be fried and	put	round. Note. Cyder instead of
The New Family Receipt-Book	the taste. Perch and Tench.	Put	them in cold water, boil
The New Family Receipt-Book	them stand till cold, then	put	them into a stone jar,
The New Family Receipt-Book	fire till it thickens, then	put	it into the fish, sew
The New Family Receipt-Book	it up; butter should be	put	over in little bits; bake
The New Family Receipt-Book	an inch thick, season and	put	them into papers, twist them
The New Family Receipt-Book	peppers, lay in a few bay-leaves,	put	It close in a pan,
The New Family Receipt-Book	drain it from the gravy,	put	it in the pots to
The New Family Receipt-Book	and cover with butter, bake	put	the spawn in. When cold
The New Family Receipt-Book	a little of the butter	put	it into the pots. Beat

Figure 14: Context Table

Finally, the **parameter selection panel (Figure 15)** allows users to **easily filter** all the contexts that have been found.

The Search Panel is divided into three main sections: Base Parameters, Include Parameters, and Exclude Parameters. Each section contains input fields for Words, Prefixes, Suffixes, and Advanced search options. The Base Parameters section also includes a Word/Phrase field, Left/Right/Alphabetic filters, and a Word Type dropdown menu. The Include and Exclude sections have radio button options for Part of Speech (POS) tags: CC, CD, DT, EX, FW, IN, JJ, and JJR.

Figure 15: Search Panel

- **Base Parameters:** These are the **essential parameters** required for any search and **cannot be left empty**. For this reason, they are assigned **default values** when the user opens the tab. All other parameters are initially left empty.

Word/Phrase

This is where users type the **word, phrase, or expression** they wish to extract from the selected texts. The system is not currently designed to handle multiple search terms at once, although that functionality could be added if needed by the research team.

Left & Right

These fields allow users to define (by typing or using the up/down arrows) the **number of words to display on each side** of the target term. The values can range from **5 to 50**. If a value lower than 5 or higher than 50 is entered, it will automatically revert to the **minimum or maximum default** value.

Alph:

This button simply **sorts the contexts alphabetically**. If not activated, contexts are displayed in their **order of appearance**.

Word Type:

This field allows users to specify the **type of word** they want to search for. It can be used in two ways:

1. To search for a **specific word** with a **specific word type**, useful when the same word may have different grammatical functions depending on the context.
2. To search for all instances of a **specific word type** without entering anything in the *Word/Phrase* field. This second method is more **computationally intensive** and will take longer than searching by word or phrase alone.

Include Parameters

This section allows users to add **inclusion parameters**—that is, conditions that **must be met** for a context to be included in the table.

Words: Specifies **words or phrases** that must appear in every context retrieved.

Prefixes & Suffixes: Used when at least one word in the context should **start or end** in a certain way. There is **no need to include the hyphen** ('-')—the program interprets it correctly.

POS (Part-of-Speech): Allows users to select which **word types** should be included in the contexts. These can be selected by scrolling and checking the appropriate **checkboxes**.

Advanced: This option allows users to combine the above criteria while also specifying the **position** where each element should appear, using a key:value format. Words and POS tags are automatically recognised. However, to distinguish between prefixes and suffixes in this field, you must now **manually include a hyphen**:

- Use a hyphen **before** a prefix (e.g., -pre)
- Use a hyphen **after** a suffix (e.g., ing-)

Exclude Parameters

This section lets users set **exclusion parameters**, meaning elements that **must not appear** in any retrieved context. Multiple values can be added, separated by commas.

Words: Defines **words or phrases** to be excluded from all contexts.

Prefixes & Suffixes: Excludes contexts where any word matches a specified **prefix or suffix**.

POS (Part-of-Speech): Allows the user to indicate which **word types** should **not** be included. Selection is made via scrollable checkboxes.

Advanced: Like the **Include** section, this allows for exclusion based on **position** within the context using a key:value format.

Words and POS tags are automatically detected, but to distinguish between suffixes and prefixes, you **must** use a hyphen:

- Prefixes: -pre
- Suffixes: ing-

Full Text Tab

The **Full Text** tab is designed to display the document **in its entirety**, exactly as it appears in its original form. This feature is especially important because the **content area** (see **Figure 13**) is limited in space and, more importantly, the formatting and layout of the text are often altered during **tokenisation** for processing.

This tab allows users to **select and read** any text—whether temporarily uploaded or retrieved through a search—in full detail and without structural distortion.

The screenshot shows the 'Full Text' tab in a web application. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'DiCoS-LA' and links for 'Home', 'Search', 'KWIC', 'Full text', and 'Analytics'. Below the navigation bar, the 'Full Text' section is displayed. On the left, there is a table with two columns: '# Title'. The table contains six rows of document titles. On the right, there is a large text area displaying the full text of the selected document, which is 'The New Family Receipt-Book, containing seven hundred truly valuable receipts in various branches of domestic economy'. The text is formatted with bold headings and includes various recipes and instructions.

#	Title
1	The New Family Receipt-Book, containing seven hundred truly valuable receipts in various branches of domestic economy
2	The family friend, a young woman's companion; or, housekeeper's instructor: containing a very complete collection of original and approved receipts in every branch of cookery, confectionary, &c. &c.
3	The modern cookery: written upon the most approved and economical principles, and in which every receipt has stood the test of experience.
4	The Virginia House-Wife. Method is the soul of management
5	The cook's complete guide, on the principles of frugality, comfort, and elegance: including the art of carving and the most approved method of setting-out a table, explained by numerous copper-plate engravings: instructions for preserving health and attaining old age: with directions for breeding and fattening all sorts of poultry and for the management of bees, rabbits, pigs, &c. &c.; rules for cultivating a garden and numerous useful miscellaneous receipts
6	The complete economical cook, and frugal housewife: an entirely new system of domestic cookery, containing approved directions for purchasing, preserving, and cooking, also, trussing & carving: preparing soups, gravies, sauces, made dishes, potting, pickling, &c. with directions for pastry and confectionery. Likewise the art of making British wines, horewinn bakens, &c.

The New Family Receipt-Book, containing seven hundred truly valuable receipts in various branches of domestic economy

FISH
To boil Turbot.
The turbot kettle must be of a proper size, and in the nicest order. Set the fish in cold water to cover it completely, throw a handful of salt and one glass of vinegar into it, let it gradually boil, be very careful that there fall no blacks, but skim it well, and preserve the beauty of the colour. Serve it garnished with a complete fringe of curled parsley, lemon and horse radish. The sauce must be the finest lobster, and anchovy butter, and plain butter, served plentifully in separate tureens.

To stew Lamprey—as at Worcester.
After cleaning the fish carefully, remove the cartilage which runs down the back, and season with a small quantity of cloves, mace, nutmeg, pepper and pimento; put it in a small stew-pot with very strong beef gravy, with port and equal quantity of madeira or sherry.
It must be covered—stew till tender, then take out the lamprey and keep hot, while you boil up the liquor with two or three anchovies chopped and some flour and butter, strain the gravy through a sieve, and add lemon juice and some made mustard. Serve with slices of bread and horse radish.
Eels, seals, and carp, done the same way, are excellent. When there is spawn, it must be fried and put round.
Note. Cyder instead of white wine will do in common.

Eel Pye.
Cut the eels in lengths of two or three inches, season with pepper and salt, and place in the dish, with some bits of butter and a little water—and cover it with paste.

Spitchcock Eels.
Take a large one, leave the skin on, cut it in pieces of four inches long, open it on the belly side and clean it nicely—wipe it dry, and then wet it with a beaten egg, and strew it over on both sides with chopped parsley, pepper, salt, a very little sage and a bit of mace pounded fine and mixed with tire seasoning. Rub the gridron with a bit of suet, and broil the fish of a fine colour.
Serve with anchovy and butter for sauce.

Fried Eels.
If small, they should be curled round and fried, being first dipped in egg and crumbs o bread.

Bolled Eels.
The small ones are preferable, do them in a small quantity of water, with a good deal of parsley, which should be served up with them and me liquor.
Serve chopped parsley and butter for sauce.

Eel Broth.
Very nourishing for the sick.
As above; but to be stewed two hours, and an onion, and pepper-corns added—salt to taste.

Collared Eel.
Bone a large eel, but don't skin it, mix pepper, salt, mace, pimento, and a clove or two, in the finest powder, and rub over the whole inside, roll it tight, and bind it with a coarse tape. Boil it in salt and water till enough, then add vinegar, and when cold, keep the collar in pickle. Serve it whole or in slices, garnished with parsley. Chopped sage, parsley, and a little thyme, knotted marjoram, and savory, mixed with the spices, greatly improve the taste.

Perch and Tench.
Put them in cold water, boil them carefully, and serve with melted butter and soy.

Figure 16: Full Text Tab

The **table on the left** is used to select the texts, while the **large text area** on the right displays the document for reading.

Finally, as seen previously in **Figure 10**, clicking the **blue Search** button will execute the context search. If the **grey Reset** button is clicked instead, the search panel will return to its **initial state**, with all parameters set to their **default values** or cleared

Analytics Tab

The **Analytics** tab enables users to perform additional types of analysis beyond the main one (contextual search). Specifically, it offers three different analytical tools: **Collocations**, **Word List**, and **N-grams**. These features aim to enhance the application's utility for the **research community**.

To switch between these types of analysis, users simply click the **blue button** labeled with each type. Each section displays a **dedicated table** containing relevant data. Navigation within the tables is done using the **Previous** and **Next** buttons to move between pages, as each table is limited to **1,000 rows** for performance reasons.

Each analytical table also includes its own **search panel**:

- Click **Search** to execute a query.
- Click **Reset** to return all filters to their **default values**, just as in the **KWIC panel**.

Lastly, as in the KWIC panel, users can **select the documents** they want to analyse using the **Documents checkbox**.

Collocations

The screenshot shows the 'Analytics Panel' in the DICO-S-LA application. On the left, there is a 'Documents' sidebar with several checkboxes and text descriptions of documents. The main area is titled 'Collocations' and contains a 'Collocations Table' with the following data:

Rank	Freq	Freq(L)	Freq(R)	Stat	Collocate
1	2237	0	0	9165.75	a little
2	889	0	0	7322.41	an hour
3	894	0	0	6200.89	should be
4	3003	0	0	6151.11	in a
5	852	0	0	5772.58	may be
6	679	0	0	5483.89	they are
7	1346	0	0	5459.67	pound of
8	1236	0	0	5155.94	plint of
9	1871	0	0	5018.50	into a
10	670	0	0	3930.53	cold water
11	2059	0	0	3899.45	with a
12	884	0	0	3723.49	let it

Below the table is a 'Search Parameters' section with the following fields: Search Term (empty), Left (1), Right (1), Min. Frequency (1), Sort by (Stat), and Order (Default). There are 'Reset' and 'Search' buttons at the bottom right of this section.

Figure 17: Collocations

The **Collocations** section (Figure 17) displays a **table of contents** listing the different collocational patterns found in the selected texts. By default, the table shows **all identified collocations**, ranked according to their **statistical score (stat)**. The **collocate** column lists the word that appears in collocation with the search term.

The panel allows users to **search for a specific term**. The table then displays all collocations involving that word, indicating whether the collocate appears to the **left or right** and showing its

frequency.

This feature has been refined and improved compared to similar functions in other tools: the system displays both **left and right frequency counts** for each collocate.

Users can set:

- The **span** (i.e., how many words to the left or right are considered part of the collocational window),
- And the **minimum frequency threshold** for a collocation to appear in the results.

Additionally, the table can be **sorted** by any column and users can choose the **sort order** (default or reversed).

Word List

The screenshot shows the DiCoS-LA interface. The top navigation bar includes 'DiCoS-LA', 'Home', 'Search', 'KWIC', 'Full text', and 'Analytics'. The 'Analytics Panel' is visible, with tabs for 'Collocations', 'Word List', and 'N-grams'. The 'Word List' tab is selected, showing a table with the following data:

Rank	Freq	Word
10001	1	uncorked
10002	1	WINES
10003	1	rhenish
10004	1	agitate
10005	1	aa
10006	1	vat
10007	1	Frontiniac
10008	1	ferments
10009	1	cur
10010	1	rants
10011	1	qua
10012	1	duce

Below the table, there are 'Previous' and 'Next' buttons, and 'Page 2 of 2'. The 'Word List Parameters' section includes a 'Word' input field, a 'Min. Frequency' input field set to '1', a 'Sort by' dropdown menu set to 'Freq', and an 'Order' dropdown menu set to 'Default'. There are also 'Reset' and 'Search' buttons.

Figure 18: Word List

In the **Word List** section, all the words from the selected texts are displayed, along with their **rank** and **frequency**.

Users can search for a **specific word**, set a **minimum frequency threshold**, and choose the **sorting order**.

N-grams

Rank	Freq	Range	N-gram
1	1	2	FISH To
2	1	2	boil Turbot
3	1	2	Turbot The
4	1	2	The turbot
5	1	2	turbot kettle
6	1	2	kettle must
7	1	2	ricest order
8	1	2	order Set
9	1	2	completely throw
10	1	2	there fall
11	1	2	fall no
12	1	2	no blacke

Figure 19: N-grams

This section allows users to search for **n-grams** and view their **frequency** and **rank**. The search panel lets users input specific terms, filter results by **frequency** and **rank**, and search for terms that appear in a **specific position** within the n-gram, as well as set the **sorting order**

Navigation Bar (Navbar)

Figure 20: Navbar

The **navigation bar** allows users to move through the application. Links to tabs such as **Search**, **KWIC**, **Full Text**, or **Analytics** are only enabled **after certain actions are performed**, in order to protect the web environment and control event flow.

For example, in the **Figure 20** shown, the navigation bar does **not display the Search tab**—this is because the context search was performed using either **added** or **temporarily opened documents**.

In this case, the **top-right corner** does not show the usual **Sign Up** and **Log In** buttons. Instead, a **user options icon** and **user image** appear—this is from a test account used during functionality testing.

Beneath the user image, a **thin coloured line** appears indicating the **user's access level**. In this example, the line is **orange**, which corresponds to **editor-level users**. There are four colour codes in total:

- **Blue:** Registered users without special permissions
- **Green:** Users with permission to consult the corpus
- **Orange:** Users with both consultation and **editor privileges**, meaning they can **upload files to corpora** or **create new ones**

- **Red: Administrator users**, who have **full access** to the application and can modify both system functions and user roles

Only **administrators** are allowed to delete corpora or files. They are also the **only ones who can delete users or assign permissions**. Therefore, any permission request must be submitted to an administrator (though the exact process for doing this is still under discussion).

User Options

User options refer to the set of features **accessible to all users**, including **those who are not registered** in the application. These functions are currently simple and limited in scope.

Figure 21: User Options

As shown in **Figure 21**, once a user has logged into the application, an additional option appears: **Settings**. The **user's profile image** and **username** are also displayed, along with a **Log out** button to end the session.

The **Language** option is still under discussion. The idea is to integrate an **external API** to translate the application interface (but **not** the uploaded texts) from English into the user's selected language.

Dark Theme

The **Dark Theme** can be activated from the **user options panel**, switching the interface to **dark mode**.

As shown in **Figure 22**, this mode removes many of the application's distinctive colours, reducing the palette to a minimum. The purpose is to **reduce visual strain**, especially when using the app for extended periods with light backgrounds

Figure 22: Dark Theme Example

Settings

The **Settings** section includes all the tools a user needs to:

- Manage their **appearance preferences** within the application,
- Configure their **email address** and **password**,
- View their **user level** and **role** in the system,
- And check their **permissions** for each of the corpora uploaded to DiCoS-LA.

The **Users** tab is highlighted in **red** in Figure 22 for explanatory purposes, but it will **not be available** to most users. This section is **only visible to administrators**, as it provides access to **permission and user management** functions for all registered users of the application.

Figure 22: Settings – Profile

Figure 22 shows the **Profile view**, designed to allow users to:

- **Select a profile image** (if none is chosen, a default image will be used),
- View their **username**, which is a unique identifier tied to all their personal data, including corpus access, saved searches, and uploaded files. Each uploaded or modified file is tagged with the **username** of the last user to modify it.
- **Full Name** is where the user enters their full legal name.
- **Display Name** is the name that will appear within the application—this is used for display purposes only.
- **Bio** refers to a short biography. It is **not visible to other users**, except administrators. It serves as an internal profile reference for the user.

Figure 23: Settings – Security

In **Figure 23**, users can **change their account’s security settings**.

The **Contact** section refers to the user’s **email address**, which can be:

- **Reviewed** by clicking the **eye icon**, or
- **Edited** by clicking the **pencil icon**

Security allows users to change their password. To do so, simply click on the blue-highlighted phrase. This will open the popup window shown in **Figure 24**, triggering an email to be sent to the user’s address with a verification code. That code must then be entered in the application in a second popup window that appears immediately afterwards.

Figure 24: ‘Password’ Popup Window

Figure 25: 'Verification Code' Popup Window

The code must be entered within **5 minutes**—after that time, it will expire. If it does, users must click **Resend code** to receive a new one. Once the code is entered, clicking **Submit** will allow the user to **set a new password** for their account.

This same process is also used to **reset the password** in case it has been forgotten during login, as will be explained in later sections.

Figure 26: Settings – 'Level/Role'

The **Level/Role** tab shown above is intended solely for reviewing user information. Here, users can check their **access level**—which essentially defines their permissions within the application—and their assigned **role**.

The role is primarily useful for **administrators**, helping them identify and manage the types of users in the system.

The next tab is **Corpus** (Figure 27), where users can view the **status of different corpora**. Access varies depending on the user.

A user may have **view-only** access, **editing privileges** (which include access), or **no permissions at all**, in which case the corpus will **not appear as an option** when clicking the corresponding button in the Home window.

Figure 27: Corpus

Finally, Figure 28 shows the **Users tab**, which is once again **only accessible to administrator-level users**.

Figure 28: Settings – 'Users'

This tab allows administrators to **manage all registered users** within the application.

By clicking on the corresponding buttons, they can modify each user's **access rights** or **editing permissions** for individual corpora.

They can also assign a **role** or **access level**, and even **delete a user** from the system.

User deletion requires **double confirmation** to prevent accidental removal..

Sign Up

Sign Up es uno de los botones que podemos ver en la barra de navegación antes de iniciar sesión, con este, podremos crearnos nuestro propio usuario dentro del sistema, rellenando los datos que aparecen en el breve formulario de la *Figura 29*. El cual solo podremos enviar si todos los datos han sido rellenados correctamente y no existen duplicados para email ni para *username*.

Join DiCoS-LA ×

Creating an account on **DiCoS-LA** allows you to save your own searches, download results and even access corpora and upload your own files, if you acquire the appropriate permissions.

Username

Password

Password Confirmation

E-mail

DiCoS-LA may use your email address to send you authentication messages as well with information regarding your account.

Have an account? [Log In](#)

Figure 29: 'Log In' Popup Window

The application will display **popup notifications** to inform users of duplicate accounts or other issues.

Once the login credentials are accepted, a **verification code** is sent to the registered email address.

This code must be entered in a window like the one shown in **Figure 25**, where it will be verified to complete the login process.

Log In

The **Log In window** allows users to access the application with their credentials.

If a user forgets their username or password, they can click on **'Trouble logging in?'** to recover them.

If no account has been created yet, users can either close the window by clicking the **'X'** or click **'Don't have an account? Sign Up'** to be redirected to the registration form.

The image shows a login popup window with a white background and a dark border. At the top right, there is a small 'x' icon for closing the window. The title 'Log In to DiCoS-LA' is centered at the top in a blue font. Below the title, there are two input fields: 'Username' and 'Password'. The 'Password' field has an eye icon on the right side to toggle visibility. Below the password field, there is a link 'Trouble logging in?' in blue. At the bottom, there is a wide, light gray button labeled 'Log In' and a link 'Don't have an account? Sign Up' in blue.

Figure 30: 'Sign Up' Popup Window